

Training And Development: Pre-Requisite For Employee's Efficiency for National Growth and Sustainability

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Abstract: *The study emphasizes on training as the means to improve knowledge and skills, and to change attitudes or behavior. It is one of the most important potential motivators which can lead to many possible benefits for both individuals and the organization. Based on that, the study employed survey design in form of cross sectional study through systematic random sampling. The sample size of three hundred and fifty [350] employees were selected by applying the method of sampling conducted by Slovin 1960. Research instrument used was a structured questionnaire, a five-point Likert scale method, while the instrument was content validated and tested using Cronbach's Alpha 0.821. The raw data were presented and analyzed using simple percentages. The data was collected through two procedures: the primary and secondary sources. Result of the study proves that there is significant relationship between training, development and efficiency of local government employees in Lagos State of Nigeria. The study concluded that the Lagos State local government's nature of work is mainly rendering services to the public, the need for continuous training and development of its human resources is crucial and vital, taking into consideration the rapid technological advancement. And recommended that identification of training needs should be done more professionally in conjunction with the line managers, as well as the individuals involved together with the Human Resource Department.*

Key Words: Taylor's Theory, Training, Development, Efficiency, human- capital, Sustainability

Introduction

Human Resources development had played a considerable role in the economic development worldwide; therefore, the developed nations such as United States of America, Britain and Japan among others have paid serious attention to human capital development. It can therefore be said that a developing country like Nigeria, with its rich natural resources and the essential financial support can also experience such economic success if proper attention is given to human resource. It is thus seen that in Nigeria the government is taking adequate steps to ensure that people acquire the necessary knowledge and skills.

The importance of manpower development could be situated vis-à-vis economic development. This is because manpower development captures the actual meaning of development in that it is people centred (World Bank 1991; Grawboski and Shields [2001]). In addition, it involves the building of capacity and harnessing the State's human resource which constitute a sine-qua-non for development. The above advantage was vividly conceptualized by Harbison (1973), when he stated that:

"Human resources constitute the ultimate basis for wealth of nations...

A country which is unable to develop the skills and knowledge of its people and to utilize them effectively in the national economy will be unable to develop anything else".

Politically, there is no doubt that a country which fails to adequately develop the manpower would be doing so at the expense of her socio-economic and political stability. Omodia (2004) asserts that the dysfunctional use of the nation's human resource among the youths in propelling political instability when he stated that:

"...there has been a situation in which the Nigerian youths especially, those of poor family background were used as tools for disrupting the political democratic system through rigging, thuggery and ethnic conflicts. These factors of rigging, thuggery in addition to economic mismanagement, personal ambition or selfishness among others, were the factors that terminated the First and Second Republic".

Thus, manpower development could help the youths in the development of self and in improving the quality of their political participation. It has been argued that effective poverty alleviation scheme must involve the

development and utilization of local resource including human for solving local problems (Robb 2000 & Omodia 2005). Thus, manpower development is central to solving the present problem of poverty in Nigeria.

Nwachukwu (2007) also sees training as the process of increasing human efficiency through which people are offered the opportunity to acquire new skills and current knowledge required, in carrying out various specialized tasks in their places of work. Efficiency therefore can be referred to as the amount or level of successful role achievement; it is determined by ability and motivation. Ability here means that the individual possesses power and key elements as intelligence, manual skills, personality, attitudes, interests and values to perform different tasks. While, human capital means the human resources of an organisation or business concern which include skilled and unskilled employees and management staff.

Since the early 1980s, the Nigerian education system has witnessed an unprecedented increase in population. A few years earlier and in response to this challenge, the Federal Government in 1976 through Act No.7 established the National Teachers Institute (2001, 2002). The enabling Act mandated the Institute to: provide refresher and upgrading courses for teaching personnel; to organize workshops, seminars and conferences; conduct examinations; carry out research; formulate policies and initiate programs that would lead to the improvement in the quality and content of education in the country. Therefore, Training, both physically, socially, intellectually and mentally are very essential. Nothing gets done without man-power. Among other scholars that highlighted the usefulness of capital development are Akintayo (1996), Oguntimehin (2001) and Graig (1976). They identified the functions of training and development as follows:

- increase productivity, improves the quality of work; improves skills, knowledge, understanding and attitude
- enhance the use of tools and machine
- reduce waste, accidents, turnover, lateness, absenteeism and other overhead costs
- eliminate obsolescence in skills, technologies, methods, products, capital management
- brings incumbents to that level of performance needed for the job
- enhance the implementation of new policies and regulations
- Prepare people for achievement, improve man-power development and ensure the survival and growth of the enterprise.

Empowered employees require new knowledge and skills; therefore, organizations need to invest heavily in training and education of their employees in areas such as: management, communications, teamwork requirements, process analysis and other issues that affect employee effectiveness, efficiency and safety. Training plans should be based upon job skill requirements and strategic initiatives of the organization.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria many organizations meet their needs for training in an ad hoc and haphazard way. Training in these organizations is more or less unplanned and unsystematic. Other organizations however set about identifying their training needs, then design and implement training activities in a rational manner, and finally assess results of training. Using the Human Development Index for 2010, Nigeria was ranked 142 out of 169 countries (UNDP, 2010), in which the statistics suggest that indices for development are lacking and ranked Nigeria among the poorest countries in the world.

Another reason is the Lack of understanding of both the concepts and methods for manpower development. Especially, the Political leadership lacks understanding of manpower training needs including some management staff often than not misunderstand the potentials in manpower training and staff development, such that they take it as a palliative measure put in place to complement employees' salaries. This often leads to the sacrifice of the real objective of training and development plans on the altar of corruption.

Objective of the Study

- The study seeks to evaluate the role of training on employees' efficiency in Lagos State of Nigeria
- To highlight the advantages of training and development for national development
- Recommend measures to improve the current training and development programs in Nigeria for human capital and national development.

Methodology

The population of the study comprised of all the employees in five Local governments in Lagos State of Nigeria such as: Shomolu, Kosofe, Oshodi/isolo, Ibeju-Lekki and Alimosho local government, that having employees population of over 2,915 out of over 10,000 employees of all the Lagos State local governments, irrespective of gender, status, years of service and age. The population figure is at 2010 by Lagos Bureau of Statistics, Ministry of Planning and Budget, The Secretariat Alausa, Ikeja, Lagos [MPM Field Report, January [2012]. The study employed survey design in form of cross sectional study through systematic random sampling. This method involved selecting every 5th employee from the sample of the required number of respondents needed for the study. The sample size of three hundred and fifty [350] employees were selected by applying the method of sampling conducted by Slovin 1960. The instrument used was a structured questionnaire, a five-point Likert scale method, while the instrument was content validated and tested using Cronbach's Alpha 0.821. The raw data were presented and analyzed using simple percentages. The data was collected through two procedures: the primary and secondary sources. The secondary sources included already existing records dealing with various aspects of previous work that made up of published and unpublished works: books, internet, articles, journals etc. The primary sources on the other hand were through questionnaires, which were self-administered with the help of research assistant.

Concepts Analysis, Definition and Explanation

Taylor's Theory

In the 20th century F. W. Taylor, the father of scientific management, believed that in the same way that there is a best machine for each job, there is also a best working method by which people should undertake their jobs. He considered that all work processes could be analyzed into discrete tasks and that by scientific methods, it is possible to find the 'one best way' to perform each task. Mullins (2010) asserts that Taylor was concerned with finding more efficient methods and procedures for co-ordination and control of work. He set out a number of principles to guide management and these principles can be summarized as:

- The development of a true science for each person's work;
- The scientific selection, training and development of workers;
- Co-operation with the workers to ensure work is carried out in the prescribed way; and
- The division of work and responsibility between management and the workers

Taylor's theory is clearly seen in the relationship between training and employee performance which shows that adequate training can lead to improvement in employee performance. At this juncture, it is pertinent to know what training, development and efficiency are all about.

Training, Development and Efficiency

Armstrong [2003], training can be defined as the planned and systematic modification of behavior through learning events, programs and instruction, which enable individuals to achieve a desired level of knowledge, skills and competence needed to carry out their assigned work effectively. It is a well-known fact that training enhances skill, knowledge, ability and competence [SKAC] and ultimately workers' effectiveness and productivity in organization (G. A. Cole, 2002).

Many organizations in Nigeria and indeed the public sector engage in training and development of staff and have departments, units and sectors in charge of training. Lagos State is one of such organization that has been practicing training since its beginning and particularly for the past five (5) years – (2005-2010). Some authors use the terms “training” and “development” as synonyms. However, some view the two concepts as being different. Jones, George and Hill (2000), believe that training primarily focuses on teaching members of an organization how to perform their current jobs and helping them acquire the knowledge and skills they need to be effectively performed.

In order to sustain economic growth and efficiency, it is important to optimize the input of employees to the aims and goals of the organizations. The importance of training as a central function of management has long been known by leading writers. Training is any learning activity which is directed towards acquisition of specific knowledge and skills for the purpose of an occupation or task, (Cole 2000).

Development is the gradual realization or growth of a person’s ability and potential [through training or experience] or growth of something, so that he [it] becomes bigger or more advanced thereby becoming useful and suited for the planned and desired goal or objective of the organization. While, efficiency can be referred to as the amount or level of successful role achievement in an organization which is determined by ability and motivation, ability here means that the individual possesses power and key elements as intelligence, manual skills, personality, attitudes, interests and values to perform different tasks.

Training Needs Assessment

A need is not a want or a desire. It is a gap between “what is” and “what ought to be” (CIPMN, 2007). There are three levels of needs assessment: organizational analysis, task analysis and individual analysis:

- Organizational analysis looks at the effectiveness of the organization and determines where training is needed and under what conditions it will be conducted.
- Task analysis provides data about a job or a group of jobs and the knowledge, skills, attitudes and abilities needed to achieve optimum performance.
- While, Individual analysis, analyzes how well the individual employee is doing the job and determines which employees need training and what kind through the needs assessment criteria:
- Performance evaluation - Identifies weaknesses and areas of improvement.
- Performance problems - Productivity, absenteeism or tardiness, accidents, grievances, waste, product quality, down time, repairs, equipment utilization, customer complaints.
- Observation - Observe both behavior and the results of the behavior.
- Work samples - Observe products generated.
- Interviews - Talk to manager, supervisor and employee. Ask employee about what he/she believes and the needs to learn.
- Questionnaire - Written form of the interview, tests must measure, job-related qualities such as job knowledge and skills.
- Attitude surveys - Measures morale, motivation, and satisfaction.
- Training progress charts - Up-to-date listing of current skills.

Training Needs Assessment is the study done in order to design and develop appropriate instructional and informational programs and materials (Rossett, 1989; Rossett & Sheldon, 2001).

Plan and Design Training

This stage in the systematic approach is therefore concerned with planning the best use of available training resources, and the design of a wide range of training activities. These have to be planned within constraints such as budgets, operational demands, facilities, availability of personnel and so on. A training intervention takes account of the full extent of training that will be needed to help people improve their efficiency. One can plan these for groups or for individuals, and they can vary in duration from a few days to a year or more. A training program often includes courses but, by themselves, courses rarely attend in full to training needs. A complete training program may include: on the job training, distance learning and Computer-based training.

Designing training refers to the application of appropriate training technique to devise learning opportunities within the context of a training program. Planning training should be based on a clear and specific requirement, which has been discussed and agreed with the client. This involves;

- Deciding who needs to be trained.
- Establishing the number of people for whom training is needed
- Specifying the aim of the training they will undertake
- Utilizing available resources
- Recognizing important constraints which may limit what can be achieved.(Ghosh 2005)

Determining Training Objectives and Training Plan

After these analyses have been done, it is easier for the training objectives to be established and also to know what the learners must be able to do after the training program.

McKenna and Beech (2002:110) in their book “Human Resource Management-A Concise Analysis”, it is stated that “It is important that a sound basis is established for other associated elements of Human Resource Management practice, such as: performance management (appraisal), reward management (motivation) combined with training and development”. What this means is that training and development itself cannot help in total employee development without the complement of employee appraisal and motivation.

One of the things to consider in designing a training program is what the program is to accomplish, that is the objectives. In other words a training program cannot be designed until what that program is to accomplish is known. It is imperative for organizations to realize that in designing a training program it is equally important to consider what the trainees should know or be able to do after the training is completed. Training objectives should however be attainable and measurable. A training program is successful if the objectives are achieved. Zaccarelli (2010) outlines the process of planning training as:

Develop a Training Plan

Once attainable and measurable training objectives have been considered, a training plan can be developed. This planning tool provides a step-by-step written document for others to follow. A training plan can be either a complete training program or just one task. The training plan details the course content, resources required method of training, who should do the training and who should be trained.

Design a Training Lesson

Once a training plan outlining general program requirements has been developed, the organization will need to concentrate on specific segments of that plan. This is done with the use of a training lesson. Generally, there is one training lesson for each training session. This means if ten sessions are planned, ten training lessons must be developed. A training lesson serves the following purpose;

- It provides a content outline for the lesson
- It suggests activities/specific instructions which will help to make training easier
- It defines suggested time to be spent on each segment within the se

Select the Trainer(S)

Who is going to train? Who is a good communicator and has the necessary knowledge/skill to train? What should the trainer do to get the trainees ready for the training? These are the questions to be addressed when selecting a trainer.

Prepare the Trainer (S)

Training is one of the most important things any organization does. As a result, the personnel responsible for training must be given adequate training themselves, as well as equip them with the necessary logistics. Remotely linked to this, trainees must also be concerned and prepared for the learning experience. There are various types of training that an organization may adopt depending on the main objectives of training. They are: Refresher training, on-the – job training, learning by doing mentoring, vestibule training, behavior modeling, business exercise, group training and understudy training

Selecting Training Methods

New training methods appear every year, while some are well founded in learning theory or models of behavior change (e.g behavior modeling). Others result more from technological than theoretical developments (e.g. presentation software, use of animation and sound, computer-based business simulations). Training methods can be classified in three ways: Information presentation, simulation methods, or on-the-job training.

- Information Presentation Technique include lectures, conferences, correspondence courses, videos/compact disks (CDs), distant learning, interactive multimedia (CDs/DVDs), and Internet, intelligent tutoring, and organization development-systematic, long-range programs of organizational improvement.
- Simulation Methods include the case method, role playing, behavior modeling, interactive simulations for virtual teams, virtual reality, the in-basket technique, and business simulations.
- On-the-Job Training Methods include orientation training, apprenticeships, on-the-job training, near-the-job training (using identical equipment but away from the job itself), job rotation, committee assignments (or junior executive boards), understudy assignments, on-the-job coaching, and performance management.

In choosing the training method (or combination of methods) that best fits a given situation, first define carefully what you wish to teach. That is the purpose of needs assessment phase. Only then one can choose a method that best fits these requirements. To be useful, the method should meet the minimal conditions needed for effective learning to take place; that is, the training method should:

- Motivate the trainee to improve his or her performance
- Clearly illustrate desired skills
- Allow the trainee to participate actively
- Provide an opportunity to practice.

The systematic approach to training includes: analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation stages. With Acro-Train, one can develop and edit at four separate levels in the curriculum development process (course, module, topic, exercise and assessments).

Training Development with Acro Train

The above diagram represents the analysis of training and development using Acro Train method. Sources: <http://www.acroservices.com/newAS/files/news/systematic.htm>

Development

Development takes the form of learning activities that prepare people to exercise wider or increased responsibilities. In development program there is an emphasis on self-directed learning as described above, personal development planning (together with learning contracts) and planned learning from experience.

Stages of personal development planning

- Analyze current situation and development needs. This can be done as part of a performance management process.
- Set goals. These include Improving performance in the current job, improving skills, extending relevant knowledge, developing specified areas of competence, moving across or upwards in the organization, or preparing for changes in the current role.
- Prepare action plan. The action plan sets out what needs to be done and how it will be done under headings such as outcomes expected (learning objectives), the development activities, the responsibility for development (what individuals are expected to do and the support they will get from their manager. (Randall W. Schuler and Susan E. Jackson, 2006).

Importance of Employees Training and Development

Economic Development: The importance of manpower development could be situated vis-à-vis economic development. This is because manpower development captures the actual meaning of development in that it is people centred (World Bank 1991; Grawboski and Shields 2002). In addition, it involves the building of capacity and harnessing the State's human resource which constitute a sine-qua-non for development. The above advantage was vividly conceptualized by Harbison (1973), when he stated that:

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people and to utilize them effectively in the national economy will be
unable to develop anything else”.*

Political Stability: There is no doubt that a country which fails to adequately develop the manpower would be doing so at the expense of her socio-economic and political stability. In the aspect of political stability, Omodia (2004), stressed the dysfunctional use of the nation's human resource among the youths in propelling political instability when he stated that:

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Thus, manpower development could help the youths in the development of self and in improving the quality of their political participation.

Poverty Alleviation: It has been argued that effective poverty alleviation scheme must involve the development and utilization of local resource including human for solving local problems (Robb [2000] & Omodia [2005]. Thus, manpower development is central to solving the present problem of poverty in Nigeria.

Advantages of Training

The purpose of training is mainly to improve knowledge and skills, and to change attitudes or behavior. It is one of the most important potential motivators which can lead to many possible benefits for both individuals and the organization. Changing technology requires that employees possess the knowledge, skills and abilities needed to cope with new processes and production techniques. According to Cole (2002) training can achieve:

- Employees who receive training have increased confidence and motivation

- Training eliminates risks because trained personnel are able to make better and economic use of material and equipment thereby reducing and avoiding waste
- Training brings a sense of security at the workplace which reduces labor turnover and absenteeism is avoided
- Training helps to manage change by increasing the understanding and involvement of employees in the change process and also provides the skills and abilities needed to adjust to new situations
- Provide recognition, enhanced responsibility and the possibility of increased pay and Promotion
- Give a feeling of personal satisfaction and achievement, and broaden opportunities for career progression and
- Help to improve the availability and quality of staff.

Analysis of Data and Discussion of Findings

Table 1 Frequency Showing Lagos State Local Governments Having Training and Development Programs for their Employees

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid YES	240	91.3	91.3	91.3
NO	23	8.7	8.7	100.0
Total	263	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

From table above shows 240(91.3%) of the respondents said yes that the Local Government has training and development programs for their employees while 23(8.7%) said no they do not have. The result shows that the local governments have training and development programs for their employees.

Table 2: Frequency Showing Kinds of Programs Embark by LGs

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid In-House Training	200	76.0	76.0	76.0
International Conference/Workshops	9	3.4	3.4	79.5
National Conferences/Workshops	40	15.2	15.2	94.7
Other	14	5.3	5.3	100.0
Total	263	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

From table above 200(76%) of the respondents identified In-House training as the program existing in their local governments, 9(3.4%) identified International Conference/Workshops, 40(15.2%) identified National Conferences/Workshops while 14(5.3%) identified other in the local government. That is the In-House training is the most common training embarked by the Local government in Lagos State.

Table 3: Frequency of Participation in Training Program in Local Government

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid YES	59	22.4	22.4	22.4
NO	204	77.6	77.6	100.0
Total	263	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

From table above shows that 59(22.4%) of the respondents have participated in training programs, while 204(77.6%) have not participated in any program. this means that most of respondents have not participated in any training program in the local government

Table 4: Frequency Showing Relevance of Training to the Present Job

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 100% relevant	210	79.8	79.8	79.8
75% relevant	30	11.4	11.4	91.3
50% relevant	10	3.8	3.8	95.1
25% relevant	13	4.9	4.9	100.0
Total	263	100.0	100.0	

Table above shows that 210(79.8%) of the respondents saw training in their present job 100 percent relevant, 30(11.4%) saw it 75 percent relevant, 10(3.8%) see it 50 percent relevant while 13(4.9%) see it 25 percent relevant. Hence most of the respondents saw training very relevant to their present job.

Table 5: Relationship between Training and the Performance of LG Employees

Items	SA	A	D	SD	U
1 Training helps me to be open to changes	120(45.6%)	80(30.4%)	25(9.5%)	13(4.9%)	25(9.5%)
2 Training assists me to deal effectively with pressure	111(42.2%)	99(37.6%)	32(12.2%)	10(3.8%)	11(4.2%)
3 It helps me to inspire, motive and guide others towards goal Accomplishment	150(57%)	100(38%)	13(4.9%)		
4 Training helps me to develop leadership skills	152(57.8%)	92(35%)	10(3.8%)	5(1.9%)	4(1.5%)
5 Training helps me achieve quality outcomes	143(54.4%)	99(37.6%)	11(4.2%)	5(1.9%)	5(1.9%)
6 It helps me to anticipate and meet the needs of students, parents, colleagues and the management	92(35%)	142(54%)	13(4.9%)	7(2.7%)	9(3.4%)
7 It helps me consistently develop and sustain cooperative working relationship	130(49.4%)	104(39.5%)	11(4.2%)	9(3.4%)	9(3.4%)
8 Training assets me to identify, analyze and take critical decision	124(47.1%)	113(43%)	13(4.9%)	9(3.4%)	4(1.5%)
9 It brings me up-to-date on changing technology and pedagogy	101(38.4%)	111(42.2%)	10(3.8%)	19(7.2%)	22(8.4%)
10 It helps me eliminate unnecessary and prolonged delays in completing work assignments	116(44.1%)	107(40.7%)	26(9.9%)		14(5.3%)

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

Table 5 above shows the relationship between training and the performance of local government employees in items in the table. The item 1 in the table shows that most of the respondents strongly agreed that training helps them to be open to changes. Item 2 shows that most of the respondents strongly agreed that training assists them to deal effectively with pressure. Item 3 shows that most of the respondents also strongly agreed that training helps them to inspire, motivate and guide others towards goal accomplishment.

Item 4 shows that most of the respondents strongly agreed that training helps them to develop leadership skills. Item 5 shows that most of the respondents strongly agreed that training helps them achieve quality outcomes. Item 6 shows that most of the respondents agreed that training helps them to anticipate and meet the needs of students, parents, colleagues and the management. Item 7 shows that most of the respondents strongly agreed that training helps them to consistently develop and sustain cooperative working relationship. Item 8 shows that most of the respondents strongly agreed that training assets them to identify, analyze and take critical decision. Item 9 shows that most of the respondents agreed that training brings them up-to-date on changing technology and pedagogy while item 10 also shows that most of the respondents strongly agreed that training helps them eliminate unnecessary and prolonged delays in completing work assignments.

Test of Hypotheses

Ho: There is no significant relationship between training, development and efficiency of Local Government employees. In testing this hypothesis using the Unstandardized Coefficients

Decision Rule

$$R = 0.887$$

$$F = 478.506$$

$$R^2 = 0.786$$

$$\text{Adjusted } R = 0.785.$$

$$\text{GDP} = 1.113 + 0.742 T + 0.0673D$$

$$\text{S.E} = (0.144) \quad (0.032) \quad (0.040)$$

The result shows that there is positive relationship between the two independent variables and the dependent variable since the parameters has positive signs. It also shows that the specified model has a high coefficient of determination. This can be seen from R-squared (R^2) of 78.6 percent and the adjusted R-squared of about 78.5 percent. The R-squared shows the percentage of variation in the dependent variable that was accounted for by variations in the independent variables. The fitness of every regression result is based on its R-squared.

The F-statistic value (478.506) shows that the overall model is statistically significant at 5 % levels of significance. This is because it is greater than the critical value of 3 at 5 percent level of significant. This means that all the explanatory variables simultaneously explain the variations in the dependent variable. Also, all the variables are statistically significant at 95 % confidence interval. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypotheses accepted accordingly. Hence, there is significant relationship between training, development and efficiency of local government employees.

Conclusion

The findings of this research indicated that Lagos State local government's nature of work is mainly rendering services to the public. This makes continuous training and development of its human resource crucial and vital, taking into consideration the rapid technological advancement. From the results of the study, it can be concluded that Lagos State local government certainly had a well-established policy to invest in the training and

development of employees, however the processes involved in training are not being duly followed. There is need to organize training programs from time to time for the employees to update their knowledge and skills and to ensure maximum efficiency and productivity in Lagos State and in Nigeria at large. While, Employees who realized the need to develop themselves through formal education in order to be abreast with modern technological advances can be sponsored by their Local governments with full salary payment or allowed to be self-sponsored on part time basis with specially considerations on the job allocation.

Recommendations

- Identification of training needs should be done more professionally in conjunction with the line managers, the individuals involved together with the Human Resource Department
- Objectives should be SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Timely) and unambiguous, and should develop individual as well as meet the needs of the local governments
- Performance appraisal information system which is used yearly at the local government to assess employees' performance and efficiency should provide specific information to employees about their performance problems and ways they can improve their performance.
- Training needs should be considered on the basis of overall local government's objectives. The goals of the local governments should determine what training programs are to be organized for staff.
- The local government's career planning involves should match an individual's career aspirations with the opportunities available in the organization

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